

FAiR

Finding Agreement
in Return

**DELIVERABLE 1.1
DATA MANAGEMENT
PLAN (Update M15)**

December 2024

DELIVERABLE D1.1: DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (UPDATE M15)

PROJECT OVERVIEW

Project Title	Finding Agreement in Return
Project Acronym	FAiR
Grant Agreement No	101094828
Start Date of Project	01.05.2023
Duration of Project	42 months
Project Coordinator	Arjen Leerkes
Title of Deliverable	Data Management Plan (Update M15)
Deliverable Number	D1.1
Dissemination Level	Public
Type of Document	Deliverable
Work Package	WP1
Version	3
Expected Delivery Date	July 31 st 2024
	V3: December 5 th 2024
Authors	Ana Maria Torres Chedraui (EUR)
Reviewers	Bozhidar Ivanov (EUR) Joanna Mania (EUR)

FUNDING

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement 101094828

STATEMENT OF ORIGINALITY

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both.

HISTORY OF CHANGES

Version	Date	Change
V2	11-06-2024	<p>Mid-term update (M15)</p> <p>2.1. Specified additional data to be re-used</p> <p>2.2. Added more columns to the tables summarizing the data generated and re-used in the project</p> <p>2.5. Added additional information on table summarizing the origin/provenance of the data</p> <p>2.6. and 3.1.1. Streamlined the answers to these questions</p> <p>3.1.2. Added more details about metadata and mandatory metadata fields</p> <p>3.1.3. Keywords added</p> <p>3.2.1. Added screenshot of FAiR community in Zenodo. Deleted unnecessary information</p> <p>3.2.2. Streamlined the answer to this question</p> <p>3.3.1. Added classification of data based on access possibilities</p> <p>3.3.3. Replaced “metadata” for “data”, as the question refers to “data”</p>

		<p>3.3.5. Streamlined the answer to this question</p> <p>3.4.1. Added some information on the purpose of the metadata</p> <p>3.4.2. Streamlined the answer to this question</p> <p>3.4.3. Added further information on Github and its connections with Zenodo</p> <p>3.5.1. Added more data formats and the language in which the data, metadata and outputs will be published</p> <p>3.6.1. Added detailed information on Readme Files, Codebook, Scripts, Folder structure and naming conventions</p> <p>3.6.5. Added additional points on data quality</p> <p>5.1. Deleted abbreviation “EUR” and used full-name “Erasmus University Rotterdam”</p> <p>5.3. Added that Privacy Officers and Legal Advisors will have an advisory role together with Data Stewards from Erasmus University Rotterdam</p> <p>5.4. Added definition of “personal and sensitive data”. This was previously mentioned somewhere else, but here fits better.</p> <p>6.1. Added different storage places for research data, including local and central</p> <p>7.1. Added information on information about Ethics Approvals for the data collections. Added information and table on verification protocol</p> <p>8.1. Streamlined the answer to this question.</p>
V3	2-12-2024	<p>Following the European Commission’s review of the project, we have made the following changes:</p> <p>3.3.1. Specified that if testimonial videos are produced, anonymization techniques (e.g., voice distortion and face covering) will be considered to protect individuals featured in the videos. If necessary, subcontracting options may be explored to ensure proper implementation of these techniques. The decision to produce such videos will consider factors such as their necessity, ethical implications, and financial constraints.</p> <p>4.2. Clarified that DOIs will only be obtained after the EC has approved the deliverables.</p>

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
2. DATA SUMMARY	6
3. FAIR DATA.....	15
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata.....	15
3.2 MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE – REPOSITORY	17
3.3 MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE – DATA.....	17
3.4 MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE – METADATA	19
3.5 Making data interoperable	19
3.6 Increase data re-use	20
4. OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS	22
5. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	22
6. DATA SECURITY	23
7. ETHICS	24
8. OTHER ISSUES	25

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Horizon Europe-funded project FAiR (Finding Agreement in Return) aims to generate new insights into migration governance, in particular into the factors and processes that foster or impede the legitimacy and effectiveness of Europe's intergovernmental return and alternatives to return policies. To this purpose, consortium partners will conduct fieldwork in 5 non-EU+ countries (Georgia, Iraq, Niger, and Turkey) and in 10-12 EU+ countries (Germany, Italy, Poland, Switzerland, Austria, France, Sweden, the Netherlands, the United Kingdom, Spain, and Greece). The project will use qualitative and quantitative methods, including interviews, focus groups, observations, discourse and document analysis, regression analysis, and survey experiments.

By bringing together stakeholders in the EU+ and non-EU+ countries, FAiR will develop an index to measure Europe's return policies (MIREX); a survey experiment on public support for alternatives to return policies; guidelines to improve the human rights monitoring of enforced return and a negotiation game to help reach agreement on return.

The present DMP specifies the management of the data that will be collected and re-used in the project. In particular, it focuses on how data will be processed, stored, shared and deleted in accordance with [General Data Protection Regulation \(GDPR\)](#) rules. It starts with an overview of the type, format and provenance of data which is crucial because data handling varies based on these factors. Next, it discusses the strategies for making data and other research outputs findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAiR). The DMP also covers resource allocation for achieving FAiRness and data security measures for recovery, storage, sharing, and long-term data preservation. Lastly, it briefly touches on ethical considerations related to data sharing and long-term data preservation.

The DMP is a dynamic document that will be updated during the project. This version corresponds to an update done in Month 15 of the project. Further updates will come in months 27 and 42 of the project.

2. DATA SUMMARY

The Data Summary gives an overview of the data collected and generated by the project

2.1. Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded

Work Packages 3, 8 will re-use the following data:

- Cassarino's inventory of bilateral agreements linked to readmission (2022): <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/VKBCBR>
- European Migration Network's report on bilateral readmission agreements (2022): https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-10/EMN_inventory_for_bilateral_readmission.pdf
- Dataset on return provisions in EU Preferential Trade Agreements between EU and non-EU states: <https://zenodo.org/record/7837954>
- Micro and Macro-level data on migration, return and various other indicators: Eurostat, Eurobarometer, World Bank, Freedom House, Transparency International, Center for Systemic Peace, OECD, ILO, amongst others.

All this data will be re-used to apply new methodologies that reduce measurement bias on Eurostat data on return. Furthermore, this data will be merged with newly collected data on prevalent discourses about return in non-EU countries, human rights monitoring of return, issue linkage of bilateral return frameworks (i.e. trade), the use of certain procedures in the negotiation (e.g. stakeholders involved, monitoring procedures, the inclusion of feedback / learning mechanisms). This 'new' dataset will serve to identify and assess different negotiation strategies with non-EU countries, and determinants of compliance with return frameworks.

For Work Packages 3 to 8, we will re-use policy documents, international agreements, and national legislation (including preparatory works, debates, and speeches). We will also use NGO reports, and media documents (e.g.

news reports, editorials, interviews, social media, article blogs, press case studies). The aim of reusing this data is twofold: first, to compile an inventory of current policies and practices, and second, to identify pertinent discussions and approaches related to return and potential alternatives.

For Work Packages 4 and 5, in particular, we will re-use administrative forms and applications. The purpose of this re-use is to understand how returns work in practice, as well as gain insights into the procedural aspects and documentation involved in the return process.

For Work Package 8 in particular, we will re-use data on macro-level state indicators from various sources (e.g. World Bank, Eurostat, Freedom House) on migration in- and out-flows, colonial ties, exports, imports, GDP, colonial ties, democracy, political terror, development aid, life expectancy, etc. This data is needed for assessing the policy and non-policy drivers of return and its alternatives.

For the Migrant Return Indicator (MIREX) that will be delivered in Work Package 9, FAiR partners are examining the relevance of the following datasets, that would be re-used:

- Demig Policy Data (Migration Institute): <https://www.migrationinstitute.org/data/demig-data/demig-policy-1>
- Data on detention and other immigration control regimes (Global Detention Project): <https://www.globaldetentionproject.org/about>
- Indicators on Good Migration Governance (Admigov Advancing Alternative Migration Governance): https://admigov.eu/upload/Deliverable_74_Indicators_of_GMG.pdf
- The Immigration Policies in Comparison (IMPIC) (<http://www.impic-project.eu>)

2.2. What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

The overview that follows is not exhaustive and will be updated as the research progresses. The tables below contain the types and formats of the data that will be generated and (potentially) re-used during the project.

GENERATED DATA							
WP	Data	Type	Formats	Considerations	Size	Origin	Data Access
3 4 5 6 7	Interviews, transcripts	Text and audio	.mp3, .mp4, .odt, .docx, .pdf (with UTF8 encoding to facilitate readability)	Informed consent, pseudonymization, anonymization, content curation, data sharing	<10GB	(G)	Metadata (O) Recordings (C) Pseudonymized/Anonymized transcripts or digitalized notes (R) Raw transcripts (C)
3 4 5 6 7 9	Focus groups, (co-creation) workshops, roundtables: recordings/audio or visual materials (when applicable), notes and minutes	Text and audio	.mp3, .mp4, .odt, .docx, .pdf (with UTF8 encoding to facilitate readability)	Informed consent, pseudonymization, anonymization, content curation, data sharing	<10GB	(G)	Metadata (O) Pseudonymized/Anonymized transcripts or digitalized notes/minutes (R) Raw transcripts/notes/minutes/recordings/audio (C)

3 5	Dataset of coded bilateral and EU return and readmission agreements and implementation mechanisms	Text and Tabular	.csv, .xlsx, .dta, .sav	Publicly available	<10GB	(G)	Metadata (O) Dataset (O) Codebook (O)
6	A behavioural experiment on alternatives to return and attitudes to migration	Tabular	.csv, .xlsx, .dta, .sav	Informed consent, anonymization, codebooks, data sharing	<10GB	(G)	Metadata (O)) Raw dataset (R) Processed dataset (O) Codebook (O)
7	Field study, observation to a forced return operation	Text	.odt, .docx, .pdf (with UTF8 encoding to facilitate readability)	Informed consent, anonymization	<1GB	(G)	Metadata (O)
8	Consolidated datasets with no bias data on return and with quantified data on policy and non-policy factors influencing return, as well as pull-in factors of non-return	Tabular	.csv, .xlsx, .dta, .sav	Data citation	<10GB	(G)	Analysis script (O) Codebook (O) Consolidated dataset (O)
9	Indicators on return policies that will be compiled in the Return Policy Index (MIREX)	Tabular	.csv, .xlsx, .dta, .sav	Publicly available	<10GB	(G)	Metadata (O) Dataset (O) Codebook (O)
9	Photo statements on migrant and practitioners' experiences with (non-) return	Visual and text	.jpeg format .docx, .odt and .pdf formats (with UTF8 encoding to facilitate readability)	Informed consent, anonymization	>10GB	(G)	Anonymized/Pseudonimized photo statements (O) Raw data (C)

Origin: RE - reused, G - generated, Data Access: O - Open access, R - Restricted access, C - Closed access and/or deleted data, NA - not applicable

RE-USED DATA							
WP	Data	Type	Formats	Considerations	Size	Origin	Data Access
3 4 5 6 7	Policy documents, international agreements and national legislation	Text	.docx, .pdf, .html	Publicly available. In case necessary, permission for access will be requested	<10GB	Various sources (RE)	NA
3 4 5 6 7	NGO reports and media documents	Text, audio, and/or audiovisual	.pdf, .docx, .html, .mp4, .mp3, .wav	Publicly available. In case necessary, permission for access will be requested	<10GB	Various sources (RE)	NA
5 7	Administrative forms and applications	Text	.docx, .pdf, .html	Publicly available. In case necessary, permission for access will be requested	<10GB	Various sources (RE)	NA
3 8	Cassarino's inventory of bilateral agreements linked to readmission	Tabular	.xls	Publicly available, Data citation	<1GB	Cassarino (RE)	NA
3 8	European Migration Network's report on bilateral readmission agreements.	Tabular and text	.pdf	Publicly available, Data citation	<1GB	European Migration Network (RE)	NA
3 8	Dataset on return provisions in EU Preferential Trade Agreements between EU and non-EU states	Tabular	.dta	Publicly available, Data citation	<10GB	Lavenex, Lutz, Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik (RE)	NA
3 8	Micro and macro-level data on migration, return and other	Tabular	.csv, .xlsx, .sav, .dta	Publicly available, Data citation	<10GB	Eurobarometer, Eurostat, World Bank,	NA

9	indicators					Freedom House, Transparency International, Center for Systemic Peace, OECD, ILO, amongst others (RE)	
---	------------	--	--	--	--	--	--

Origin: RE - reused, G - generated, *Data Access:* O - Open access, R - Restricted access, C – Closed access and/or deleted data, NA – not applicable

RE-USED DATA UNDER CONSIDERATION							
WP	Data	Type	Formats	Considerations	Size	Origin	Data Access
9	Demig Policy Data (Migration Institute)	Tabular	.dta, .xlsx	Publicly available	<10GB	Demig (RE)	NA
9	Data on detention and other immigration control regimes (Global Detention Project)	Tabular and text	.html	Publicly available	<10GB	Global Detention Project (RE)	NA
9	Indicators on Good Migration Governance (Admigov Advancing Alternative Migration Governance)	Text and tabular	.pdf	Publicly available	<10GB	Admigov (RE)	NA
9	The Immigration Policies in Comparison (IMPIC)	Tabular	.dta	Publicly available	<10GB	IMPIC (RE)	NA

Origin: RE - reused, G - generated, *Data Access:* O - Open access, R - Restricted access, C – Closed access and/or deleted data, NA – not applicable

2.3. What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

FAiR will re-use Eurostat data on return in order to apply innovative methodologies that allow to overcome existing bias on this data. We will also integrate Eurostat data with pre-existing and newly generated data on determinants to return with the purpose of generating the MIREX (Return Policy Index). The MIREX, a consolidated dataset, will serve as a powerful tool to significantly enhance policy-making in migration governance, supporting evidence-based decision-making and improving the effectiveness of policies (objective 2). Moreover, this consolidated data will serve

to assess and cooperation on return and suggest new cooperation avenues (objective 4).

Through the behavioural experiments, we will assess the public's acceptance of alternatives to return and the factors influencing it, as well as the impact of enforced return on public attitudes towards migration. Based on the results of the experiments and some expert interviews, FAiR will assess the feasibility of return alternatives (objective 5).

The qualitative data collected throughout the project will generate novel insights into the institutional, economic, political, and social factors that either facilitate or impede the willingness and capacity of non-EU states to reach agreements and comply with return and readmission policies (objective 3). Stakeholder workshops will enable us to evaluate and formulate recommendations for effective and sustainable returns and alternatives to return policies (objective 6).

Finally, re-used and newly generated data will assist FAiR in presenting a synthesised theoretical framework that combines rational choice and sociological institutionalism that will assist international actors in predicting and developing feasible return strategies.

2.4. What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

Since the project includes audio, audiovisual materials, photographs, a behavioural experiment with a sample of 1,000 to 1,500 respondents per country (10 EU+ countries), various datasets, and interview transcripts, we expect that the size of the data will be large and could even exceed 250 GB.

2.5. What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

The generated and re-used data will come from various sources, as specified in the tables below:

Generated data	Origin/Provenance
Indicators on return policies that will be compiled in the Return Policy Index (MIREX)	Reports from consulted country experts in 10-12 EU+ countries
A behavioural experiment on alternatives to return and attitudes to migration	Conjoint and behavioural online experiment in 10 EU+ countries which will involve a representative sample of the general population (1,000-1,500 respondents per country).
Field study: observation of a forced return operation	Physical observation of a forced return operation
Consolidated datasets with no bias data on return and with quantified data on policy and non-policy factors influencing return, as well as pull-in factors of non-return	<p>Including, but not exclusively:</p> <p>Eurostat: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/product/page/MIGR_EIORD_custom_4257524 https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/product/page/MIGR_EIRTN_custom_4257928</p> <p>Cassarino, Jean-Pierre, 2022, "Inventory of the Bilateral Agreements Linked to Readmission", Harvard Dataverse, V2: https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/VKBCBR</p> <p>European Migration Network (EMN) (2022). Bilateral Readmission Agreements. EMN Inform. Brussels: European Migration Network: https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-10/EMN_inventory_for_bilateral_readmission.pdf</p> <p>Sandra Lavenex, Philipp Lutz, & Paula Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik. (2023). Migration Provisions in Preferential Trade</p>

	<p>Agreements (MITA) Dataset (1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/7837954</p> <p>World Bank: https://databank.worldbank.org/home.aspx https://www.knomad.org/data/remittances</p> <p>Freedom House: https://freedomhouse.org/report/freedom-world</p> <p>GESIS Survey Data Curation department: https://www.gesis.org/en/eurobarometer-data-service/search-data-access/eb-trends-trend-files/list-of-trends/polit-issues-national</p> <p>Center for Systemic Peace: https://www.systemicpeace.org/inscrdata.html</p> <p>Transparency International: https://www.transparency.org/en/cpi/2023</p> <p>The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD): https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/development/data/oecd-international-development-statistics/official-and-private-flows_data-00072-en</p> <p>International Labour Organization: https://ilostat ilo.org/data/</p> <p>Research and Expertise on the World Economy (CEPII): http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/bdd_modele/bdd_modele_it em.asp?id=8 http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/bdd_modele/bdd_modele_it em.asp?id=19</p> <p>Eurostat, UN-DESA, OECD: https://doi.org/10.2908/MIGR_POP1CTZ</p>
<p>Interviews: transcripts, audio and/or audio-visual recordings.</p>	<p>Former and current government officials at the national and local levels, policy practitioners, public officials at embassies and state institutions involved in the production of ID and travel documents in EU and non-EU countries</p> <p>Migrant organizations, diaspora groups, migrants and employers in EU countries</p> <p>Civil society organizations, community leaders and returnees in non-EU countries</p> <p>IOs and bodies monitoring return and readmission to third countries</p> <p>NGOs and human rights activists</p>
<p>Focus groups and (co-creation) workshops, roundtables: notes, audio and/or audio-visual recordings</p>	<p>Former and current government officials at the national and local levels, policy practitioners, public officials at embassies and state institutions involved in the production of ID and travel documents in EU and non-EU countries.</p>

	<p>Migrant organizations, diaspora groups, migrants and employers in EU countries</p> <p>Civil society organizations, community leaders and returnees in non-EU countries</p> <p>IOs and bodies monitoring return and readmission to third countries</p> <p>NGOs and human rights activists</p> <p>Media organizations in non-EU countries.</p> <p>The observations in particular will come from a forced return operation organised by Frontex via a chartered flight.</p>
Bilateral and EU return and readmission agreements and implementation mechanisms	Coding of bilateral and EU-wide agreements on return and readmission
Photo statements on migrant and practitioners' experiences with (non-) return	Photos taken by FAiR consortium partners during their fieldwork

Re-used data	Origin/Provenance
Cassarino's inventory of bilateral agreements linked to readmission (2022)	Cassarino, Jean-Pierre, 2022, "Inventory of the Bilateral Agreements Linked to Readmission", Harvard Dataverse, V2: https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/VKBCBR
European Migration Network's report on bilateral readmission agreements (2022)	European Migration Network (EMN) (2022). Bilateral Readmission Agreements. EMN Inform. Brussels: European Migration Network: https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-10/EMN_inventory_for_bilateral_readmission.pdf
Dataset on return provisions in EU Preferential Trade Agreements between EU and non-EU states	Sandra Lavenex, Philipp Lutz, & Paula Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik. (2023). Migration Provisions in Preferential Trade Agreements (MITA) Dataset (1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/7837954
Micro and Macro-level data on migration, return and various indicators	<p>Including, but not exclusively:</p> <p>Eurostat: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/product/page/MIGR_EIORD_custom_4257524 https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/product/page/MIGR_EIRTN_custom_4257928</p> <p>World Bank: https://databank.worldbank.org/home.aspx https://www.knomad.org/data/remittances</p> <p>Freedom House: https://freedomhouse.org/report/freedom-world</p> <p>GESIS Survey Data Curation department:</p>

	<p>https://www.gesis.org/en/eurobarometer-data-service/search-data-access/eb-trends-trend-files/list-of-trends/polit-issues-national</p> <p>Center for Systemic Peace: https://www.systemicpeace.org/inscrdata.html</p> <p>Transparency International: https://www.transparency.org/en/cpi/2023</p> <p>The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD): https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/development/data/oecd-international-development-statistics/official-and-private-flows_data-00072-en</p> <p>International Labour Organization: https://ilostat.ilo.org/data/</p> <p>Research and Expertise on the World Economy (CEPII): http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/bdd_modele/bdd_modele_it_em.asp?id=8 http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/bdd_modele/bdd_modele_it_em.asp?id=19</p> <p>Eurostat, UN-DESA, OECD: https://doi.org/10.2908/MIGR_POP1CTZ</p>
Policy documents, international agreements, and national legislation	Official repositories, public bodies websites
Administrative forms and applications	Embassies and consular offices websites
NGO reports, and media documents	NGOs websites, Nexis Uni (media material)

Re-used data (under consideration)	Origin/Provenance
Demig Policy Data	Migration Institute: https://www.migrationinstitute.org/data/demig-data/demig-policy-1
Data on detention and other immigration control regimes	Global Detention Project: https://www.globaldetentionproject.org/about
Indicators on Good Migration Governance	Admigov Advancing Alternative Migration Governance: https://admigov.eu/upload/Deliverable_74_Indicators_of_GMG.pdf
Dataset of Immigration Policies	The Immigration Policies in Comparison (IMPIC): http://www.impic-project.eu

2.6. To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

The data produced in the project is expected to be valuable to various stakeholders. From a policy perspective, the data will aid policymakers and practitioners in improving the formulation of return and alternative policies. For instance, unbiased return data will provide more precise estimations about return rates and will allow for targeted policies to address return deficits, while data on the acceptability of alternatives to return can inform about which alternatives to return are accepted and how other countries deal with non-return. Additionally, evidence on factors influencing return compliance can be used to engage policy makers in dialogue in and outside Europe and formalize commitments for addressing cooperation deficits. On the academic front, the data can be used by researchers to expand their analysis to include additional countries and regions worldwide, enhancing the breadth of knowledge in the field.

3. FAIR DATA

This section is related to the FAIRification process that will be followed by the Consortium

3.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1. Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

We will ensure that all the data packages, research outputs and metadata of FAiR that are publicly accessible in Zenodo will receive a DOI to ensure its findability and accessibility.

3.1.2. Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Metadata will be provided to ensure that the FAiR outputs can be consistently identified and retrieved. For this purpose, we will use as much as possible [DataCite Metadata Schema](#) or [Data Documentation Initiative](#).

Metadata will be filled out in Yoda (<https://erasmus-yoda.irods.surfsara.nl>) using the predetermined metadata form. Currently, the FAiR space in Yoda (research-fair-return) is organized with folders on a WP level. Some WP leaders have created subfolders for type of data collected and/or shared. WP leaders are free to create subfolders if necessary to organize the data of their own WP in Yoda. Metadata must be provided for each folder or subfolder. Take the following example:

Based on the example above, four metadata forms should be completed. WP leaders are responsible for ensuring that all required information in the Yoda metadata form is fully completed. This includes fields marked with an asterisk (*) in the Yoda metadata form, such as:

- Title

- Description (type of stakeholder, collection data -date, country, language used, translation needed-consortium institutions and individuals involved in the collection of the data)
- Discipline
- Language of the anonymized data (might not be the same as the language used for collecting the data)
- Keyword
- Retention period (Note: the retention period is 10 years from the end of the embargo on October 31, 2028)
- Data Classification
- Identification information of the data creator
- Data Package Access
- Any applicable License

While this information is mandatory, researchers should aim to provide as much additional information as possible as requested in the Yoda metadata form.

For quantitative data, we will prepare metadata for each dataset. Therefore, it is advisable for WP leaders to create a separate folder for each dataset to streamline metadata management and avoid unnecessary duplication.

WP leaders have the discretion to decide on the creation of metadata at the file level, in addition to folders and subfolders, especially when the work is divided among different researchers. Below is an example of a file-level metadata prepared in WP7:

Date of the interview	
Time of the interview	
Location (city/country or online)	
Participant/s and affiliations*	
Language(s) used	
Was translation of this transcript conducted externally/subcontracted?	
Interview code (Fieldwork Country_No. of interview)	
Duration of the interview	
Type of stakeholder	
Level	
Institution of interviewee	
Gender of the interviewee	

*For internal purposes only

WP leaders have the discretion to create metadata at the file level. However, as a consortium, it is only mandatory to create metadata at the (sub)folder level. There are two main reasons for this:

1. Data Backup on Yoda: To ensure we can back up the data on Yoda, the metadata at the (sub)folder level must be completed.
2. Data Accessibility and Participant Anonymity: We aim to make quantitative data available to the public and qualitative data available to external researchers. Providing metadata at the file level could potentially lead to the identification of the participant. To ensure anonymity, but also the usability of the data collected, we will make the metadata at the (sub)folder level available to the public/external researchers.

3.1.3. Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

Yes, we will provide search keywords to optimize the discovery and re-use of data, such as return and readmission agreements; EU return policy; return implementation mechanisms; irregular migration; legitimacy; alternatives to return policies; survey experiment; return policy index; human rights monitoring; discourse analysis.

3.1.4. Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Yes, metadata will be offered in formats that allow harvesting and indexing. To this purpose, we will ensure that the metadata is presented in standardized formats such as XML, JSON or similar formats supported by the repositories that will be used to share the data (see next section). In addition, we will use as much as possible the DataCite Metadata Schema or Data Documentation Initiative, we will provide access through APIs or web services and we will ensure that the metadata is consistently structured and well-documented.

3.2 MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE – REPOSITORY

3.2.1. Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

Anonymized datasets resulting from the survey experiment and determinants of return will be deposited in Zenodo with public open access. They will be published under [FAiR Community](#). Zenodo is a trusted repository according to the definition specified in the Guides for Researchers ([OpenAIRE](#)).

3.2.2. Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

At this moment, we do not foresee any additional arrangements with Zenodo which provides a persistent identifier (DOI), options for proper licensing, a preservation and data availability policy, and appropriate data protection for restricted data.

3.2.3. Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Yes, Zenodo assign Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs).

3.3 MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE – DATA

3.3.1. Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

FAiR will deal with data that has different access possibilities. Namely, open access data, restricted access data and closed access data.

Open Access

Macro level data or policy indicators are not personal or sensitive data and therefore will be made openly available. Survey data collected from individual participants can be openly shared if anonymized or pseudonymized.

Restricted Access

Interview transcripts even if anonymized, pseudonymized or summarized cannot be openly shared if the participant has not given its express consent. In addition, if participants have consented, their anonymized or pseudonymized interview transcripts or summaries will be shared with external researchers outside the consortium only. To this purpose, we will prepare some terms of use for the data that will be implemented on Zenodo to ensure that only researchers can access the data. Before accessing the data, every user will have to commit to using it solely for research purposes and to not attempting to identify the interviewees.

The photo exhibition organized by PICUM will seek the informed consent of the participants portrayed in the photos, which will comply with the [General Data Protection Regulation \(GDPR\)](#) and will address data protection rights and concerns of those involved. PICUM will detail how the photos will be used, when and where in consent forms that will be submitted to the people involved in the photos. Such consent forms will clearly state that people involved will retain the right to withdraw their consent at any moment. In addition, concerns around anonymity will be addressed in conjunction with those involved in the creation of the photos, and the photos' subjects themselves. Anonymisation techniques may include anonymising names in the photo description, hiding elements that could make the subject recognisable by others (including taking pictures from the back), editing such elements through specific digital tools, or taking pictures where the subject is not present.

If the consortium decides to produce testimonial videos, as recommended by the European Commission in its review report, anonymization techniques (e.g., voice distortion and face covering) will be considered to protect the individuals involved. If necessary, subcontracting options may be explored to ensure these techniques are properly implemented. The decision to produce testimonial videos will be made after an internal consortium discussion, considering factors such as their necessity for communication purposes, ethical implications and available financial resources.

With regards to the qualitative fieldwork that will be conducted in the project, we will ensure that all consortium partners use a standardized consent form for participant interviews/fieldwork to maintain consistent data handling.

Closed Access and/or Deletion

To uphold participant privacy, audiovisual materials or audio recordings obtained from interviews, focus groups, workshops, and similar activities will never be made publicly accessible. Instead, these materials will be safely deleted after transcription and once verified that the interview/fieldwork took place (typically within 3 weeks of the interview/fieldwork). The consequences of exposing such data can be severe, as participants may face reprisals or stigmatization due to their collaboration with the project.

3.3.2. If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

According to the GA, we will set in place an embargo of two years on all generated or re-used data in the project. We will count two years after the end of the project (October 31st of 2026), that means that it will last until October 31st 2028. This will allow the consortium partners the possibility to publish the findings in scientific journals. After the embargo period has expired (October 31st 2028), and subject to the consent of the participants, FAiR will make the data available for scientific reuse using FAIR data principles.

3.3.3. Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

The data will be available in online repositories (as indicated above) and therefore it will be accessible in this way.

3.3.4. If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

After the embargo period (October 31st 2028), the data will be made accessible through Zenodo as mentioned above. Public data will be made available without access restrictions. With explicit consent from the participants, anonymized or pseudonymized interview transcripts or a summary of them will be shared outside the consortium strictly for research purposes.

3.3.5. How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

Requests to access restricted data will be evaluated on a case-by-case basis. To guarantee that the restricted data is utilized solely for research, as consented by the participant, we will select a repository that has login protocols for Restricted Access to the data.

3.3.6. Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Since personal or sensitive data will not be shared, we do not foresee at the moment the need for a data access committee.

3.4 MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE – METADATA

3.4.1. Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

Yes, the metadata will be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0. The metadata will specify whether the data can be accessible and/or under which conditions (i.e. for research purposes only), the website where it can be downloaded or access requested.

3.4.2. How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

The data and metadata will be stored in Zenodo, which offers long-term access assurance.

3.4.3. Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

The code used for cleaning, pre-processing, and extracting features of the datasets will be made public through the project's website, Github or COMSES. In order to ensure the long-term availability, the Github repository will be integrated with Zenodo which will assign a DOI to the code (https://inbo.github.io/tutorials/tutorials/git_zenodo/). When publishing the code, we will specify the program that has to be used to run the code.

3.5 MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

3.5.1. What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

The data will be provided in specific formats to ensure clarity and facilitate its long-term usability. As indicated above, the chosen formats will be .docx, .odt or .pdf for text data, .xlsx, .dta, .sav, or .csv for tabular data, .jpeg for pictures, .wav for audio material and, .mp3 or .mp4 for audio-visual materials. These formats have been selected for various reasons. Firstly, they align with staff expertise and familiarity, enabling efficient data management and manipulation. Secondly, there is a preference for open formats that promote accessibility and interoperability. Standardized, interchangeable, and open formats are essential for sharing and archiving data, ensuring its long-term viability and usability. Additionally, the metadata, data, and other research outputs will be in English.

3.5.2. In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

We will employ the terminology used in this field of research, such as “forced return”, “voluntary return”, “enforced return”, “source countries”, “transit countries”, “destination countries”, etc. In case it is unavoidable to use uncommon or generate project specific vocabularies, we will provide mappings to more commonly used vocabularies in the field, and we will openly publish the generated vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them.

3.5.3. Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

When appropriate, qualified references will be utilized to refer to other data.

3.6 INCREASE DATA RE-USE

3.6.1. How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

Metadata

As mentioned earlier in question 3.1.2., we will organize metadata at the folder level. For qualitative data, metadata at the file level is optional. However, for quantitative data, we will provide metadata for each dataset. Therefore, it is advisable to create a separate folder for each dataset to streamline metadata management and avoid unnecessary duplication.

Readme files

We will use readme files on a WP level to briefly describe the content and structure of the (sub) folders in each WP. The read-me file can be used also to explain the difficulties in filling out the metadata Yoda forms or other information that cannot be accounted in the standardized metadata form.

Codebook for datasets and qualitative data

To ensure the re-usability of the data, we will prepare a codebook for each dataset that includes information on the methodology used to collect the data, definitions of variables, the format and file type of the data and software used to collect and/or process the data.

In case qualitative coding is used, we will also prepare a codebook that explains the meaning of the codes used in the analysis, as well as a Code-Document Table, if available, that indicates the documents or other materials in which those codes were identified.

Script for datasets

For datasets, we will prepare a script that contains the coding used to process the data, with the indication of the programme where the code should be run. If Excel or any other program is used that does not allow the creation of a script, the researcher will put in written what it has done to process the data.

Folder structure and naming conventions

Data packages will have a logical folder's structure and naming conventions, following the organization of the data in the Yoda workspace. As in Yoda we will organize the data on folders.

- Each WP will have a folder with the number and name of the WP: WP3_IntergovernmentalReturnFrameworks.
- Inside each work package folder, WP leaders will create sub-folders taking the name of the type of data collected/shared (AssistedVoluntaryReturns). Abbreviated names can be used as long as they are explained in the readme file.
- Files will be named consisting of [fieldwork country, capital letter]_[number of interview]_[abbreviation of data, capital letter]_[type of data, capital letter]_[authors abbreviation, capital letter], for example: BE_1_AVR_Transcript_AP.docx
- Files containing datasets will be named consisting of [geographical coverage, capital letter]_[name of data, capital letter]_[type of data, capital letter]_[authors abbreviation, capital letter], for example: EU_Return_Dataset_MC.xlsx

3.6.2. Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

The data that is suitable for public release, as described in section 3.3.1 above, will be made accessible to the public without any restrictions, using CC-BY or something equivalent as specified in the Grant Agreement.

3.6.3. Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes, part of the data will be useable by third parties after the end of the project by making it accessible through CC-BY domains or similar.

3.6.4. Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

Yes, the provenance of the data will be thoroughly documented in the corresponding metadata, as specified in section 3.1 above.

3.6.5. Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

FAiR will strive for data that is reliable and reproducible. To achieve this, we will ensure data quality is verified at various stages of collection, digitization, and checking. The following steps will be taken to ensure data quality:

Training and Manuals

- Data collection manuals will be developed to standardize the process. Trainings will be emphasized, particularly if the same data is being collected by different individuals or institutions across various countries.

Transcription and Translation

- When computer-assisted programs are used for transcription or translation of interviews, researchers will verify the accuracy before sharing the results with other research partners.
- Uniformity will be ensured by using standardized templates for transcriptions.
- Metadata and ReadMe files will be created to map the data and ensure its reproducibility.

Data Handling and Processing

- The design of questionnaires for interviews, concept notes for workshops, and survey experiments will be discussed with partners involved in the task to allow for feedback and improve the data collection design.
- Programs that generate written code will be used for dataset compilation to avoid human errors and ensure transparency.
- A codebook will be prepared to facilitate understanding and navigation of the data by other researchers.
- To minimize errors in the processing of quantitative data, we will check for data completeness, add value labels where needed, and double-check coding responses.

Review and Anonymization

- The corresponding team producing the data will follow a review procedure to ensure datasets and interview transcripts are sufficiently anonymized, pseudonymized, or summarized.
- Respondents will be given the opportunity to review the anonymization, pseudonymization, or summaries of their interviews to ensure they are comfortable with the process.

Research Outputs

- All deliverables will be revised by internal peer-reviewers within the consortium who will ensure the quality of the output.

3.6.6. Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

We agree and for this reason we provide answers to the questions that follow below.

4. OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS

4.1. In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

We will not re-use or generate research outputs like the examples given in the question. We will though produce open-access working papers, reports, policy briefs and handbooks. We do not foresee any limitation in the reusability of these outputs.

4.2. Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

Once the European Commission approves the project deliverables, we will strive to publish all working papers, reports, policy briefs and handbooks with a DOI. By doing so, only finalized versions will get a DOI. This will prevent confusions when identifying and tracking the final version of the deliverable.

5. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

5.1. What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?

Considering the limited size of the data that will be made available in Zenodo, the costs of making the data FAIR in the project will be free of charge. With regards to other research outputs, Erasmus University Rotterdam has open access agreements with various peer-review journals, therefore no costs for publications involving the researchers

affiliated in this institution will arise.

5.2. How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)

We have budgeted costs related to the publication of research outputs.

5.3. Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Since every partner institution is responsible for storing the data that it collects, preparing the codebook and metadata for its publication in the repository, they will all be responsible for data management in the project. Data Stewards, Privacy Officer and Legal Advisors from Erasmus University Rotterdam will have an advisory role.

5.4. How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

Zenodo will ensure the long-term preservation of the data. In addition, each partner will implement data backup systems to mitigate the risk of data loss or corruption. These backups will be maintained securely, particularly if they include sensitive or personal information. We understand sensitive or personal data as “[d]ata that can be directly or indirectly traced back to a person...” ([Guidelines for the archiving of academic research for Faculties of Behavioural and Social Sciences in The Netherlands](#), p. 6).

Although sensitive information will not be preserved, the deletion of that information will occur after the interview has been transcribed and the integrity of the interview/fieldwork has been verified which will typically occur within 3 weeks from the interview/fieldwork. Until this occur, the audio/visual recordings and any sensitive information will be maintained securely using encrypted backups and secured storage locations in accordance with [General Data Protection Regulation \(GDPR\)](#) by the partner institution that collected the data. For purposes of research integrity, the contact details of the participants will be stored in a protected vault by the partner conducting the interview for the duration of the project (until October 31st 2026).

6. DATA SECURITY

6.1. What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

Local storage solution for research data

Each partner institution is responsible for the storage of all the data that s/he is collecting, re-using or producing. When partner organizations handle confidential information, like audio/visual recordings or personal data that cannot be shared publicly, they will store it securely in an encrypted storage until it is transcribed. During this time, the research institution responsible for the data will validate the integrity of the fieldwork, ensuring that the interviews/fieldwork actually took place (on this aspect see question 7.1). After this verification and the completion of transcription (typically within 3 weeks of the interview), all audio/visual recordings will be safely deleted. For purposes of research integrity, the contact details of the participants will be stored in a protected vault by the partner conducting the interview for the duration of the project (until October 31st 2026).

When storing data, partners are expected:

- to use a robust, managed cloud storage appropriate to the sensitivity of data
- regularly backup data – this can be a automatic built-in feature of the storage tool or manually. If back up is done manually, it should occur at least once a week.
- to control access to data: The data will be shared with a closed user group within the organization, accessible to authorized user only. When available, institutions will use multifactor authentication to

ensure the accessibility of the data to authorized users only.

- to comply to the data security policies of each institution and actively strive to reduce the possibility of data breach; In the event of data breach, follow institutional data breach protocol

If partners need to transfer data, they will make the necessary arrangements. And if the data is personal and not public, they need to secure the consent of the data owner and will consider using encrypted transfer protocols, if appropriate. The consent of the owner can be secured in written form (i.e. through email, chat message) or verbally. If verbally the partner getting the authorization will document what s/he asked, when and what the person given the consent said. The personal data will have to be deleted if it is not used, when the data owner refused to participate in the fieldwork or activity s/he was contacted for, when the data owner asked for its deletion or when the data was used and is no longer relevant. Each partner will bear the responsibility of storing this personal data in a protected vault.

Central storage solution for research data

FAiR partners use SURF Yoda to share and store their anonymized/pseudonymized transcripts with FAiR partners. Access to the Yoda workspace for the FAiR project (*research-fair-return*) is limited to researchers affiliated with FAiR's partner institutions.

Central storage solution for other research outputs

Working papers, policy briefs, reports, etc are stored in the [FAiR Google Drive](#). If necessary, the Faculty Data Steward at Erasmus University Rotterdam will offer guidance regarding data storage throughout the course of the project.

6.2. Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

As mentioned above, we will store data in Zenodo which is a trusted repository to ensure its long-term preservation and curation.

7. ETHICS

7.1. Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

Erasmus University Rotterdam, as the coordinating institution, will ensure that the fieldwork undergoes an ethics review and receives approval from its Ethics Committee. If additional ethics approvals are required by partner institutions, we will seek those as well. Otherwise, we will follow the guidelines and approvals provided by the Ethics Committee at the coordinating institution.

We will use standardized informed consent forms to inform participants about the purpose of the FAiR research and how their information will be handled.

Pseudonymized or anonymized transcripts will be shared with the FAiR partner institutions involved in doing research. For this purpose, the participant will have to consent to this. In case he does not, the participant will not be interviewed. Participants will be also asked to consent if their pseudonymized, anonymized or summarized transcripts can be made available outside the consortium for research purposes only. In case s/he does not consent, the interview will still take place but the pseudonymized, anonymized or summarized transcript cannot be made available outside the consortium. The participant will be invited to give his input on his pseudonymized, anonymized or summarized transcript. In addition, the members of the consortium and the external researchers that will have access to the pseudonymized transcripts will commit not to make any attempt to identify the interviewees.

We do not expect to share sensitive or personal data (as defined in question 5.4) in or outside the consortium, but if need arises, the partner institutions will make the necessary arrangements to transfer this data safely and respecting the [General Data Protection Regulation \(GDPR\)](#) rules. All sensitive or personal data collected from interviews, observations or any other fieldwork will be safely deleted after transcription and once verified that the interview/fieldwork took place (typically within 3 weeks of the interview/fieldwork), except for the contact details of

the participants. For purposes of research integrity, the contact details of the participants will be retained and stored in a protected vault by the partner conducting the interview for the duration of the project (until October 31st 2026).

To validate the integrity of the fieldwork, partners are free to choose the verification protocol that best suits their needs. For example, one protocol could involve having multiple researchers listen to recordings of interviews conducted by others to confirm their authenticity. Any method used to verify the occurrence of the interviews should be documented, as illustrated in the table below:

WP	Task	Interview Code	Interviewer	First reviewer	Date first review	Second reviewer	Date second review	Observations
7	7.2	ES_1_FR_Transcript_AMT	Ana Maria Torres (EUR)	Laura Cleton (EUR)	25-03-2024	Nino Tartarashvili (EUR)	13-06-2024	Extracts of the recording in Spanish were confronted with the transcript. The voices of the interviewer and 1 participant were recognized.

FAiR will follow the [Guidelines for the archiving of academic research for Faculties of Behavioural and Social Sciences in The Netherlands](#) and the [ALLEA European code of conduct for research integrity](#). In addition to that, all consortium partners will abide to the [General Data Protection Regulation \(GDPR\)](#) rules throughout the project's duration, in particular when collecting data from third parties.

7.2. Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Informed consent forms will include questions about data sharing within and outside the consortium members for research purposes. We will ensure that all partners in the consortium use the same informed consent forms to ensure consistency. If the researcher deems necessary to share personal data of the participant, he will make sure that he obtains his informed consent on this aspect. Equally informed consent forms will include questions about the long-term preservation of the anonymized/pseudonymized data. Following the [Guidelines for the archiving of academic research for Faculties of Behavioural and Social Sciences in The Netherlands](#), we will preserve the pseudonymized or anonymized data for 10 years after the embargo expires (October 31st 2028). Voice or video recordings, along with any personal data, will be deleted after the interview has been transcribed and verified that the interview or fieldwork indeed occurred, typically within 3 weeks of the interview or fieldwork. For purposes of research integrity, the contact details of the participants will be stored in a protected vault by the partner conducting the interview for the duration of the project (until October 31st 2026).

8. OTHER ISSUES

8.1. Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

We will not make use of other procedures for data management.